

Synthesis and fungicidal activity of 4,4'-bis[2''-(aryl/alkylimino)-4''-oxothiazolin-3''-yl-acetamidoxy]bibenzyls and 4,4'-bis(oxadiazolymethoxy)bibenzyls

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Manuscript received 2 February 2007, revised 11 July 2008, accepted 24 September 2008

Abstract : Chemoselective facile synthesis of novel 4,4'-bis[2''-(aryl/alkylimino)-4''-oxothiazolin-3''-ylacetamidoxy]-bibenzyls (**5a-e**) and 4,4'-bis(oxadiazolymethoxy)bibenzyls (**6a-e**) are reported. Cycloaddition of chloroacetic acid on 1,2-bis[4-(2-oxo-substituted-2-thiosemicarbazinoethoxy)phenyl]ethane (**4a-e**) yielded (**5a-e**) and cyclisation of (**4a-e**) in presence of Iodine in KI gave (**6a-e**). These compounds have been evaluated for their antifungal activity.

Keywords : Bibenzyl, bryophytes, anticonvulsant, thiosemicarbazides, *Aspergillus niger*, *Fusarium oxysporum*.

Introduction

Compounds containing 1,3,4-oxadiazole^{1,2} and thiazole^{3,4} are inherently toxic to micro-organism, especially to fungi and bacteria. Thiosemicarbazides have been reported to possess antifungal^{5,6}, antibacterial⁷ and anticonvulsant⁸ properties. Literature survey⁹ have revealed that bryophytes are not damaged by fungi although they contain nutritious material like fatty acids, sterols etc. because of the presence of structural variants of bibenzyl and bisbibenzyl. It has been found that both natural and synthetic bibenzyl show antifungal activity against spore germination of *Alternaria brassicola*, *Botrytis cineria*, *Uromyces fabae*. So, in our effort to develop new bio-degradable and broad spectrum fungicides, synthesis of bibenzyl having thiazole and oxadiazole moiety is presented in this paper.

1,2-Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)ethane **1** have been synthesised by diazotisation and hydrolysis of 1,2-bis(4-aminophenyl)ethane¹⁰. Compound **1** upon refluxion with dry acetone and chloroacetic acid gave 4,4'-dimethoxy diacetate bibenzyl **2**, which on condensation with hydrazine hydrate gave 4,4'-bis(methoxycarbohydrazide)bibenzyl **3**. Compound **3** with isothiocyanate gave 4,4'-bis(methoxycarboaryl/alkylthiosemicarbazide)bibenzyl (**4a-**

e), compound **4a-e** on cyclisation with chloroacetic acid and I₂/KI yielded 4,4'-bis(2''-aryl/alkylimino-4''-oxothiazolin-3''-yl-acetamidoxy)bibenzyls (**5a-e**) and 4,4'-bis(oxadiazolymethoxy)bibenzyls (**6a-e**) respectively (Scheme 1).

Antifungal activity :

The synthesized compounds (**4a-e**, **5a-e**, **6a-e**) have been screened for their fungicidal activity against two fungal species, viz. *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium oxysporum* by the poisoned food technique¹¹ (1000, 100, 10 ppm). The number of replicate assays in each were three and six replicate controls were used. Commercial fungicide, Dithane M-45 used as standard. The antifungal screening results are summarized in Table 2.

Most of the screened compounds have significant fungitoxicity at 1000 ppm (Table 2) against both tested fungi, but their toxicity considerably decreased on dilution (100 and 10 ppm). Of the tested compounds, the most active compounds **5b**, **5d**, **6b** and **6e** displayed fungicidal action comparable with that of Dithane M-45 at 1000 ppm.

Experimental

Melting points were determined by open glass capillary method and are uncorrected. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR) spectrometer

Table 1. Physical and spectral data of compounds 4a-e, 5a-e and 6a-e

Compd.	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Molecular formula	Found (Calcd.) (%)			¹ H NMR δ (CDCl ₃)
				C	H	N	
4a	69	120	C ₃₂ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	61.12 (61.16)	5.12 (5.16)	10.9 (10.10)	2.84 (4H, s, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.2–7.5 (18H, m, ArH), 4.94 (4H, s, OCH ₂), 8.16 (2H, s, NH-C=S)
4b	58	155	C ₃₄ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂	59.28 (59.29)	5.26 (5.28)	12.20 (12.2)	2.86 (4H, s, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 3.95 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 7.20–7.72 (16H, m, ArH), 8.16 (2H, s, NH-C=S), 4.95 (4H, s, OCH ₂)
4c	62	164	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	54.11 (54.12)	6.05 (6.06)	12.03 (12.04)	2.84 (4H, s, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.12–7.5 (8H, m, ArH), 8.16 (2H, s, NH-C=S), 4.94 (4H, s, OCH ₂), 0.9 (4H, q, CH ₂), 1.2 (6H, t, CH ₃)
4d	56	136	C ₃₂ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Cl ₂	55.09 (55.10)	4.38 (4.35)	12.04 (12.05)	2.87 (4H, s, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.25–7.97 (16H, m, ArH), 8.16 (2H, s, NH-C=S), 4.94 (4H, s, OCH ₂)
4e	51	105	C ₃₄ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₄ S ₂	62.17 (62.19)	5.52 (5.52)	12.79 (12.80)	2.85 (4H, s, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.2–7.9 (16H, m, ArH), 8.16 (2H, s, NH-C=S), 4.94 (4H, s, OCH ₂), 1.3 (6H, s, CH ₃)
5a	72	210	C ₃₆ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂	61.0 (61.01)	4.55 (4.56)	11.85 (11.86)	2.84 (4H, s, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.2–7.5 (18H, m, ArH), 4.29 (4H, s, CO-CH ₂ -S), 8.12 (2H, s, NH-CO), 8.34 (2H, s, NH-N), 4.95 (4H, s, OCH ₂)
5b	74	180	C ₃₈ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₈ S ₂	59.36 (59.37)	4.7 (4.72)	10.9 (10.11)	2.86 (4H, s, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 3.95 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 7.20–7.72 (16H, m, ArH), 4.30 (4H, s, CO-CH ₂ -S), 8.13 (2H, s, NH-CO), 8.36 (2H, s, NH-N), 4.94 (4H, s, OCH ₂)
5c	68	225	C ₂₈ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂	57.91 (57.92)	5.55 (5.56)	14.47 (14.48)	2.84 (4H, s, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.2–7.5 (8H, m, ArH), 4.9 (4H, s, CO-CH ₂ -S), 8.12 (2H, s, NH-CO), 8.34 (2H, s, NH-N), 4.95 (4H, s, OCH ₂), 0.9 (4H, q, CH ₂), 1.2 (6H, t, CH ₃)
5d	62	170	C ₃₆ H ₃₀ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂ Cl ₂	55.59 (55.60)	3.88 (3.89)	10.88 (10.81)	2.87 (4H, s, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.25–7.97 (16H, m, ArH), 8.13 (2H, s, NH-CO), 8.34 (2H, s, NH-N), 4.95 (4H, s, OCH ₂)
5e	55	185	C ₃₈ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂	61.93 (61.94)	4.92 (4.93)	11.40 (11.42)	2.85 (4H, s, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.2–7.8 (16H, m, ArH), 8.12 (2H, s, NH-CO), 8.34 (2H, s, NH-N), 4.95 (4H, s, OCH ₂), 1.35 (2H, s, CH ₃)
6a	65	160	C ₃₂ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₄	68.55 (68.56)	5.03 (5.04)	14.99 (14.10)	2.85 (4H, s, acyclic CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.1–7.9 (18H, m, ArH), 4.94 (4H, s, OCH ₂), 2.21 (2H, s, NH-R)
6b	64	125	C ₃₄ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₆	55.54 (55.55)	5.54 (5.55)	13.49 (13.50)	2.86 (4H, s, CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.2–7.8 (16H, m, ArH), 3.95 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.95 (4H, s, OCH ₂)
6c	56	130	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₆	57.58 (57.59)	6.44 (6.45)	16.78 (16.79)	2.84 (4H, s, CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.1–7.5 (8H, m, ArH), 4.94 (4H, s, OCH ₂), 2.1 (2H, s, NH-R), 0.9 (4H, q, CH ₂), 1.2 (6H, t, CH ₃)
6d	58	112	C ₃₂ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₄ Cl ₂	61.05 (61.06)	4.16 (4.17)	13.35 (13.36)	2.85 (4H, s, CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.2–7.5 (16H, m, ArH), 4.95 (4H, s, OCH ₂), 2.23 (2H, s, NH-R)
6e	60	122	C ₃₄ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₄	69.37 (69.38)	5.47 (5.48)	14.27 (14.28)	2.86 (4H, s, CH ₂ CH ₂), 7.2–7.8 (16H, m, ArH), 4.95 (4H, s, OCH ₂), 2.2 (2H, s, NH-R), 1.23 (2H, s, CH ₃)

Scheme 1

in CDCl₃ using TMS as internal reference, chemical shifts are expressed in δ values.

1,2-Bis[4-(carboxymethoxy)phenyl]ethane (2) :

To a solution of 0.03 mol of ethylene bisphenol (1) in dry acetone (25 ml), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (10 g) and chloroacetic acid (0.03 mol) were added and refluxed on water-bath with stirring for 12–13 h under reduced pressure. The product was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol (yield 50%).

1,2-Bis[4-(2-hydrazino-2-oxoethoxy)phenyl]ethane (3) :

A mixture of 2 (0.03 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.06 mol) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed on steam-bath for 4.5 h. After refluxing excess of ethanol distilled off, the solid mass, thus, obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (yield 60%).

1,2-Bis[4-(2-oxo-2-substituted thiosemicarbazinoethoxy)phenyl]ethane (4a-e) :

To the solution of 3 (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 mol), phenylisothiocyanate (0.01 mol) was added with stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 5 h on a water-bath. The

resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to give **4a**. Similarly **4b**, **4c**, **4d** and **4e** were synthesized by using ethylisothiocyanate, *p*-methoxy phenylisothiocyanate, *p*-chlorophenylisothiocyanate, *p*-methylphenylisothiocyanate respectively in place of phenylisothiocyanate (yield 43%).

Table 2. Antifungal screening results of compounds **4a-e**, **5a-e** and **6a-e**

Compd.	Av% inhibition after 96 h against					
	<i>A. Niger</i>			<i>F. oxysporium</i>		
	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm
4a	61	50	22	68	52	27
4b	64	53	30	66	51	29
4c	53	42	20	50	35	18
4d	55	40	25	57	43	21
4e	58	41	32	60	45	26
5a	63	40	26	68	42	25
5b	79	52	29	72	47	33
5c	55	32	19	58	37	23
5d	78	43	32	81	54	36
5e	72	49	34	70	42	31
6a	76	47	23	70	32	18
6b	88	59	42	90	60	46
6c	71	42	21	68	38	22
6d	69	43	29	65	37	23
6e	75	35	38	77	48	34

4,4'-Bis[N-(2''-aryl/alkylimino-4''-oxothiazolin-3''-yl)acetamidoxy]bibenzyl (5a-e) :

To the solution of **4a** (0.01 mol) in acetic acid (10 ml), monochloroacetic acid (1 g) and anhydrous sodium acetate (1 g) were added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 h cooled, poured into crushed ice, the separated solid was filtered, washed thoroughly with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol to give **5a**. Similarly **5b**, **5c**, **5d** and **5e** were synthesized from **4b**, **4c**, **4d** and **4e** respectively in place of **4a** (yield 40%).

4,4'-Bis(2''-aryl/alkylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5''-methoxy)bibenzyl (6a-e) :

To compound **4a** (0.03 mol) in ethanol (30 ml), aq. NaOH (6 N, 5 ml) was added. A 10% solution of I₂ in KI was then added dropwise and the reaction mixture was kept at 10 °C. The addition of iodine was continued till the colour of I₂ persisted and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h. The solid separated on cooling was washed thoroughly with water and recrystallised from DMSO to give **6a**. Similarly **6b**, **6c**, **6d** and **6e** were synthesized by using **4b**, **4c**, **4d** and **4e** respectively in place of **4a** (yield 45%).

Yields, m.p., molecular formula, elemental analysis and spectral data of compounds (**4a-e**, **5a-e**, **6a-e**) are recorded in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

We sincerely thank Head of the Chemistry Department, Allahabad University, Allahabad for providing laboratory facilities and RSIC, CDRI, Lucknow for providing spectral data.

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